

Unleashing and Speeding Up Readers in Atomic Object Implementations

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Abstract. Providing efficient emulations of atomic read/write objects in asynchronous, crash-prone, message-passing systems is an important problem in distributed computing. Communication latency is a factor that typically dominates the performance of message-passing systems, consequently the efficiency of algorithms implementing atomic objects is measured in terms of the number of communication exchanges involved in each read and write operation. The seminal result of Attiya, Bar-Noy, and Dolev established that two pairs of communication exchanges, or equivalently two round-trip communications, are sufficient. Subsequent research examined the possibility of implementations that involve less than four exchanges. The work of Dutta et al. showed that for single-writer/multiple-reader (SWMR) settings two exchanges are sufficient, provided that the number of readers is severely constrained with respect to the number of object replicas in the system and the number of replica failures, and also showed that no two-exchange implementations of multiple-writer/multiple-reader (MWMR) objects are possible. Later research focused on providing implementations that remove the constraint on the number of readers, while having read and write operations that use variable number of communication exchanges, specifically two, three, or four exchanges.

This work presents two advances in the state-of-the-art in this area. Specifically, for SWMR and MWMR systems algorithms are given in which read operations take *two or three* exchanges. This improves on prior works where read operations took either (a) three exchanges, or (b) two or four exchanges. The number of readers in the new algorithms is *unconstrained*, and write operations take the same number of exchanges as in prior work (two for SWMR and four for MWMR settings). The correctness of algorithms is rigorously argued. The paper presents an empirical study using the NS3 simulator that compares the performance of relevant algorithms, demonstrates the practicality of the new algorithms, and identifies settings in which their performance is clearly superior.

1 Introduction

Emulating atomic [11] (or linearizable [10]) read/write objects in asynchronous, message-passing environments with crash-prone processors is a fundamental problem in distributed computing. To cope with processor failures, distributed object implementations use *redundancy* by replicating the object at multiple network locations. Replication masks failures, however it introduces the problem of consistency because operations may access different object replicas possibly containing obsolete values. Atomicity is the most intuitive consistency semantic as it provides the illusion of a single-copy object that serializes all accesses such that each read operation returns the value of the latest preceding write operation.

Background and Prior Work. The seminal work of Attiya, Bar-Noy, and Dolev [2] provided an algorithm, colloquially referred to as ABD, that implements SWMR (Single Writer, Multiple Reader) atomic objects in message-passing crash-prone asynchronous environments. Operations are ordered using logical *timestamps* associated with each value. Operations terminate provided some majority of replica servers does not crash. Writes involve a single communication round-trip involving *two* communication exchanges. Each read operation takes two rounds involving in *four* communication exchanges. Subsequently, Lynch et al. [13] showed how to implement MWMR (Multi-Writer, Multi-Reader) atomic memory where both read and write operations take two communication round trips, for a total of *four* exchanges.

Dutta et al. [3] introduced a *fast* SWMR implementation where both reads and writes involve *two* exchanges (such operations are called ‘fast’). It was shown that this is possible only when the number of readers r is constrained with respect to the number of servers s and the number of server failures f , viz. $r < \frac{s}{f} - 2$. Other works focused on relaxing the bound on the number of readers in the service by proposing hybrid approaches where some operations complete in *one* and others in *two* rounds, e.g., [4].

Georgiou et al. [6] introduced Quorum Views, client-side tools that examine the distribution of the latest value among the replicas in order to enable fast read operations (two exchanges). A SWMR algorithm, called SLIQ, was given that requires at least one single slow read per write operation, and where all writes are fast. A later work [5] generalized the client-side decision tools and presented a MWMR algorithm, called CwFR, that allows fast read operations.

Previous works considered only client-server communication round-trips. Recently, Hadjistasi et al. [9] showed that atomic operations do not necessarily require complete communication round trips, by introducing server-to-server communication. They presented a SWMR algorithm, called OHSAM, where reads take *three* exchanges: two of these are between clients and servers, and one is among servers; their MWMR algorithm, called OHMAM, uses a similar approach. These algorithms do not impose constraints on reader participation and perform a modest amount of local computation, resulting in negligible computation overhead.

Model	Algorithm	Read Exch.	Write Exch.	Read Comm.	Write Comm.
SWMR	ABD [2]	4	2	$4 \mathcal{S} $	$2 \mathcal{S} $
SWMR	OHSAM [9]	3	2	$ \mathcal{S} ^2 + 2 \mathcal{S} $	$2 \mathcal{S} $
SWMR	SLIQ [6]	2 or 4	2	$4 \mathcal{S} $	$2 \mathcal{S} $
SWMR	ERATO	2 or 3	2	$ \mathcal{S} ^2 + 3 \mathcal{S} $	$2 \mathcal{S} $
MWMR	ABD-MW [2,13]	4	4	$4 \mathcal{S} $	$4 \mathcal{S} $
MWMR	OHMAM [9]	3	4	$ \mathcal{S} ^2 + 2 \mathcal{S} $	$4 \mathcal{S} $
MWMR	CWFR [5]	2 or 4	4	$4 \mathcal{S} $	$4 \mathcal{S} $
MWMR	ERATO-MW	2 or 3	4	$ \mathcal{S} ^2 + 3 \mathcal{S} $	$4 \mathcal{S} $

Table 1. Summary of communication exchanges and communication complexities.

Contributions. We focus on the gap between one-round and two-round algorithms by presenting atomic memory algorithms where read operations can take *at most* “one and a half rounds,” i.e., complete in either *two* or *three* exchanges. Complexity results are shown in Table 1, additional details are as follows.

1. We present ERATO,⁴ *Efficient Reads for ATomic Objects*, a SWMR algorithm for atomic objects in the asynchronous message-passing model with processor crashes. We improve the *three*-exchange read protocol of OHSAM [9] to allow reads to terminate in either *two* or *three* exchanges using client-side tools, Quorum Views, from algorithm SLIQ [6]. During the second exchange, based on the distribution of the timestamps, the reader may be able to complete the read. If not, it awaits for “enough” messages from the third exchange to complete. A key idea is that when the reader is “slow” it returns the value associated with the *minimum* timestamp, i.e., the value of the previous write that is guaranteed to be complete (cf. [9] and [3]). Read operations are optimal in terms of exchanges in light of [8]. Similarly to ABD, writes take *two* exchanges. (Section 3.)

2. Using the SWMR algorithm as the basis, we develop a MWMR algorithm, ERATO-MW. The algorithm supports *three*-exchange read protocol based on [9] in combination with the iterative technique using quorum views as in [5]. Reads take either *two* or *three* exchanges. Writes are similar to ABD-MW and take *four* communication exchanges (cf. [13]). (Section 4.)

3. We simulate the algorithms using the NS3 simulator and assess their performance under practical considerations by varying the number of participants, frequency of operations, and network topologies. (Section 5.)

Improvements in latency are obtained in a trade-off for communication complexity. Simulation results suggest that in practical settings, such as data centers with well-connected servers, the communication overhead is not prohibitive.

2 Models and Definitions

We now present the model, definitions, and notations used in the paper. The system is a collection of crash-prone, asynchronous processors with unique identifiers (ids). The ids are from a totally-ordered set \mathcal{I} that is composed of three disjoint sets, set \mathcal{W} of writer ids, set \mathcal{R} of reader ids, and set \mathcal{S} of replica server ids. Each *server* maintains a copy of the object.

⁴ *Ερατώ* is a Greek Muse, and the authors thank the lovely muse for her inspiration.

Processors communicate by exchanging messages via asynchronous point-to-point reliable channels; messages may be reordered. We use the term *broadcast* as a shorthand denoting sending point-to-point messages to multiple destinations.

A quorum system over a set is a collection of subsets, called quorums, such that every pair of quorums intersects. We define a quorum system \mathbb{Q} over the set of server ids \mathcal{S} as $\mathbb{Q} = \{Q_i : Q_i \subseteq \mathcal{S}\}$; it follows that for any $Q_i, Q_j \in \mathbb{Q}$ we have $Q_i \cap Q_j \neq \emptyset$. We assume that every process in the system is aware of \mathbb{Q} .

Executions. An algorithm A is a collection of processes, where process A_p is assigned to processor $p \in \mathcal{I}$. The *state* of processor p is determined over a set of state variables, and the state of A is a vector that contains the state of each process. Algorithm A performs a *step*, when some process p (i) receives a message, (ii) performs local computation, (iii) sends a message. Each such action causes the state at p to change. An *execution* is an alternating sequence of states and actions of A starting with the initial state and ending in a state.

Failure Model. A process may crash at any point in an execution. If it crashes, then it stops taking steps; otherwise, the process is *correct*. Any subset of readers and writers may crash. A quorum $Q \in \mathbb{Q}$ is non-faulty if $\forall p \in Q, p$ is correct. Otherwise, Q is faulty. Any server may crash as long one quorum is non-faulty.

Efficiency and Message Exchanges. Efficiency of implementations is assessed in terms of *operation latency* and *message complexity*. *Latency* of an operation is determined by *computation time* and the *communication delays*. Computation time accounts for all local computation within an operation. Communication delays are measured in terms of *communication exchanges*. The protocol implementing each operation involves a collection of sends (or broadcasts) of typed messages and the corresponding receives. As defined in [9], a *communication exchange* within an execution of an operation is the set of sends and receives for the specific message type. Traditional implementations in the style of ABD [2] are structured in terms of *rounds*, each consisting of two exchanges, the first, a broadcast, is initiated by the process executing an operation, and the second, a convergecast, consists of responses to the initiator. The number of messages that a process expects during a convergecast depends on the implementation. *Message complexity* measures the worst-case total number of messages exchanged.

Atomicity. An implementation of a read or a write operation contains an *invocation* action and a *response* action. An operation π is *complete* in an execution, if it contains both the invocation and the *matching* response actions for π ; otherwise π is *incomplete*. An execution is *well formed* if any process invokes one operation at a time. We say that an operation π *precedes* an operation π' in an execution ξ , denoted by $\pi \rightarrow \pi'$, if the response step of π appears before the invocation step in π' in ξ . Two operations are *concurrent* if neither precedes the other. The correctness of an atomic read/write object implementation is defined in terms of *atomicity* (safety) and *termination* (liveness) properties. Termination requires that any operation invoked by a correct process eventually completes. Atomicity is defined following [12]. For any execution ξ , if Π is the set of all completed read and write operations in ξ , then there exists a partial order \prec on the operations in Π , s.t. the following properties are satisfied:

- A1** For any $\pi_1, \pi_2 \in \Pi$ such that $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$, it cannot be that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$.
- A2** For any write $\omega \in \Pi$ and any operation $\pi \in \Pi$, then either $\omega \prec \pi$ or $\pi \prec \omega$.
- A3** Every read operation returns the value of the last write preceding it according to \prec (or the initial value if there is no such write).

Timestamps and Quorum Views. Atomic object implementations typically use logical timestamps (or tags) associated with the written values to impose a partial order on operations that satisfies the properties A1, A2, and A3.

A *quorum view* [6] refers to the distribution of the highest timestamp among the servers, $maxTS$, that a read operation witnesses during a communication exchange, and can be used as a tool to determine the state of a write operation i.e., whether it is complete or incomplete. Suppose that during an exchange, a read ρ strictly receives timestamp and value pairs $\langle s.ts, v \rangle$ from each server $s \in Q_i$. As presented in [6], ρ can distinguish three different quorum views:

- QV(1): $\forall s \in Q_i : s.ts = maxTS$
- QV(2): $\forall Q_j \in \mathbb{Q}, i \neq j, \exists A \subseteq Q_i \cap Q_j, \text{ s.t. } A \neq \emptyset \text{ and } \forall s \in A : s.ts < maxTS$
- QV(3): $\exists s' \in Q_i : s'.ts < maxTS \text{ and } \exists Q_j \in \mathbb{Q}, i \neq j \text{ s.t. } \forall s \in Q_i \cap Q_j : s.ts = maxTS$

Fig. 1. (a) QV(1), (b) QV(2), (c) QV(3) incomplete write, (d) QV(3) complete write

For example, in Fig. 1 dark circles represent servers that contain the $maxTS$, and light ones any older timestamp. The quorum system \mathbb{Q} consists of three quorums, $\{Q_i, Q_j, Q_z\}$. If QV(1) is observed, Fig. 1(a), it means that only one timestamp is received, thus the write associated with $maxTS$ has potentially been completed. If QV(2) is observed, Fig. 1(b), this indicates that the write associated with $maxTS$ is still in progress (because older timestamps are detected in the intersections of quorums). Lastly, if QV(3) is observed, the distribution of timestamps does not provide sufficient information for the state of the write. This, because there are two possibilities as shown in Fig. 1(c) and 1(d). In Fig. 1(c) the write is incomplete while in Fig. 1(d) the write completes in quorum Q_z , however, in both executions every server in the intersection of $Q_z \cap Q_i$ replies with $maxTS$. We use quorum views as a design element in our algorithms.

3 SWMR Algorithm ERATO

We now present and analyze the SWMR algorithm ERATO.

3.1 Algorithm Description

In ERATO reads take either *two* or *three* exchanges. This is achieved by combining the *three* exchange read protocol of [9] with the use of Quorum Views of [6]. The

read protocol design aims to return the value associated with the timestamp of the last complete write operation. We refer to the three exchanges of the read protocol as E1, E2, and E3. Exchange E1 is initiated by the reader, and exchanges E2 and E3 are conducted by the servers. When the reader receive messages during E2, it analyses the timestamps to determine whether to terminate or wait for the conclusion of E3. Due to asynchrony it is possible for the message from E3 to arrive at the reader before messages from E2. In this case the reader still terminates in *three* exchanges. Similarly to ABD, writes take *two* exchanges. The code is given in Algorithm 1. We now give the details of the protocols; in referring to the numbered lines of code we use the prefix “L” to stand for “line”.

Reader Protocol. Each reader r maintain several temporary variables. Key variable include $minTS$ and $maxTS$ hold the minimum and the maximum timestamps discovered during the read operation. Sets RR and RA hold the received `readRelay` and `readAck` messages respectively. The ids of servers that sent these messages are stored in sets $RRsrv$ and $RAsrv$ respectively. The set $maxTSrv$ keeps the ids of the servers that sent a `readRelay` message with the timestamp equal to the maximum timestamp $maxTS$.

Reader r starts its operation by broadcasting a `readRequest` message to the servers (exchange E1). It then collects `readRelay` messages (from exchange E2) and `readAck` messages (from exchange E3). The reader uses counter $read_op$ to distinguish fresh message from stale message from prior operations. The messages are collected until messages of the same type are received from some quorum Q of servers (L7-11). If `readRelay` messages are received from quorum Q then the reader examines the timestamps to determine what quorum view is observed (recall Section 2). If $QV_{(1)}$ is observed, then all timestamps are the same, meaning that the write operation associated with the timestamp is complete, and it is safe to return the value associated with it without exchange E3. (L24-25). If $QV_{(2)}$ is observed, then the write associated with the maximum timestamp $maxTS$ is not complete. But because there is a sole writer, it is safe to to return the value associated with timestamp $maxTS-1$, i.e., the value of the preceding complete write, again without exchange E3 (L34-37). If $QV_{(3)}$ is observed, then the write associated with the maximum timestamp $maxTS$ is in progress or complete. Since the reader is unable to decide which case applies, it waits for the exchange E3 `readAck` messages from some quorum Q . The reader here returns the value associated with the *minimum* timestamp observed (L27-33). It is possible, due to asynchrony, that messages from E3 arrive from a quorum before enough messages from E2 are gathered. Here the reader decides as above for E3 (L12-16).

Writer Protocol. Writer w increments its local timestamp ts and broadcasts a `writeRequest` message to all servers. It completes once `writeAck` messages are received from some quorum Q (L52-56).

Server Protocol. Server s stores the value of the replica v and its associated timestamp ts . The *relays* array is used to store sets of processes that relayed to s regarding a read operation. Destinations set D is initialized to set containing all servers from every quorum that contains s . It is used for sending relay messages during exchange E2.

Algorithm 1 Reader, Writer, and Server Protocols for SWMR algorithm ERATO

```

1: At each reader  $r$ 
2: Variables:
3:  $minTS, maxTS \in \mathbb{N}; read\_op \in \mathbb{N}$  init 0
4:  $RR, RA, maxACK \subseteq \mathcal{S} \times M$ 
5:  $v \in V; RRsrv, RAsrv, maxTSrv \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ 
6: function READ
7:    $read\_op \leftarrow read\_op + 1$ 
8:    $(RR, RA, RRsrv, RAsrv) \leftarrow (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$ 
9:   bcast ( $\langle readRequest, r, read\_op \rangle$ ) to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
10:  wait until  $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RRsrv$ 
11:     $\vee Q \subseteq RAsrv$ 
12:  if ( $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RAsrv$ ) then
13:     $minTS \leftarrow \min\{(m.ts) : (s, m) \in RA$ 
14:       $\wedge s \in Q\}$ 
15:    return( $m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in RA$ 
16:       $\wedge m.ts = minTS$ )
17:  else if ( $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RRsrv$ ) then
18:     $maxTS \leftarrow \max\{(m.ts) :$ 
19:       $(s, m) \in RR \wedge s \in Q\}$ 
20:     $maxACK \leftarrow \{(s, m) \in RR :$ 
21:       $s \in Q \wedge m.ts = maxTS\}$ 
22:     $maxTSrv \leftarrow \{s \in Q :$ 
23:       $(s, m) \in maxACK\}$ 
24:    if  $Q \subseteq maxTSrv$  then **Qview1** //
25:      return( $m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in maxACK$ )
26:    if  $\exists Q' \in \mathbb{Q}, Q' \neq Q$ 
27:      s.t.  $Q' \cap Q \subseteq maxTSrv$  then
28:      **Qview3** //
29:      wait until  $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RAsrv$ 
30:       $minTS \leftarrow \min\{(m.ts) :$ 
31:         $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q\}$ 
32:      return( $m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in RA$ 
33:         $\wedge s \in Q \wedge m.ts = minTS$ )
34:    else **Qview2** //
35:       $maxACK \leftarrow \{(s, m) \in RR :$ 
36:         $s \in Q \wedge m.ts = maxTS - 1\}$ 
37:      return( $m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in maxACK$ )
38:  Upon receive  $m$  from  $s$ 
39:  if  $m.read\_op = read\_op$  then
40:    if  $m.type = readRelay$  then
41:       $RR \leftarrow RR \cup \{(s, m)\}$ 
42:       $RRsrv \leftarrow RRsrv \cup \{s\}$ 
43:    else // readAck //
44:       $RA \leftarrow RA \cup \{(s, m)\}$ 
45:       $RAsrv \leftarrow RAsrv \cup \{s\}$ 
46:  At writer  $w$ 
47: Variables:
48:  $ts \in \mathbb{N}^+, v \in V, wAck \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ 
49: Initialization:
50:  $ts \leftarrow 0, v \leftarrow \perp, wAck \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
51: function WRITE( $val : input$ )
52:    $(ts, v) \leftarrow (ts + 1, val)$ 
53:    $wAck \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
54:   bcast ( $\langle writeRequest, ts, v, w \rangle$ ) to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
55:   wait until ( $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq wAck$ )
56:   return()
57: Upon receive  $m$  from  $s$ 
58: if  $m.ts = ts$  then
59:    $wAck \leftarrow wAck \cup \{s\}$ 
60: At server  $s$ 
61: Variables:
62:  $ts \in \mathbb{N}$  init 0 ;  $v \in V$  init  $\perp$ 
63:  $D \subseteq \mathcal{S}$  init  $\{s' : Q \in \mathbb{Q} \wedge (s, s' \in Q)\}$ 
64:  $operations : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$  init  $0^{|\mathcal{R}|}$ 
65:  $relays : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{S}}$  init  $0^{|\mathcal{R}|}$ 
66: Upon receive( $\langle readRequest, r, read\_op \rangle$ )
67: bcast( $\langle readRelay, ts, v, r, read\_op, s \rangle$ )
68:   to  $D \cup r$ 
69: Upon receive( $\langle writeRequest, ts', v', w \rangle$ )
70: if ( $ts < ts'$ ) then
71:    $(ts, v) \leftarrow (ts', v')$ 
72: send ( $\langle writeAck, ts, s \rangle$ ) to  $w$ 
73: Upon receive
74:   ( $\langle readRelay, ts', v', r, read\_op, s \rangle$ )
75: if ( $ts < ts'$ ) then
76:    $(ts, v, vp) \leftarrow (ts', v')$ 
77: if ( $operations[r] < read\_op$ ) then
78:    $operations[r] \leftarrow read\_op$ 
79:    $relays[r] \leftarrow \emptyset$ .
80: if ( $operations[r] = read\_op$ ) then
81:    $relays[r] \leftarrow relays[r] \cup \{s\}$ 
82: if ( $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq relays[r_i]$ ) then
83:   send ( $\langle readAck, ts, v, read\_op, s \rangle$ )
84:   to  $r$ 

```

In exchange E1 of a read, upon receiving message $\langle readRequest, r, read_op \rangle$, the server creates a `readRelay` message, containing its ts , v , and s , and broadcasts it in exchange E2 to destinations in D and reader r (L66-68).

In exchange E2, upon receiving message $\langle readRelay, ts', v', r, read_op \rangle$ s compares its local timestamp ts with ts' . If $ts < ts'$, then s sets its local value and timestamp to those enclosed in the message (L75-76). Next, s checks if the received `readRelay` marks a new read by r , i.e., $read_op > operations[r]$. If so, then s : (a) sets its local counter for r to the enclosed one, $operations[r] = read_op$; and (b) re-initializes the relay set for r to an empty set, $relays[r] = \emptyset$ (L77-79).

It then adds the sender of the `readRelay` message to the set of servers that informed it regarding the read invoked by r (L80-81). Once `readRelay` messages are received from a quorum Q , s creates a `readAck` message and sends it to r in exchange E3 of the read (L82-84).

Within a write operation, upon receiving message $\langle \text{writeRequest}, ts', v', w \rangle$, s compares its ts to the received one. If $ts < ts'$, then s sets its local timestamp and value to those received, and sends acknowledgment to the writer (L69-72).

3.2 Correctness and Complexity

Here we prove correctness of algorithm ERATO. Termination (liveness) is satisfied with respect to our failure model: at least one quorum Q is non-faulty and each operation waits for messages from a single quorum.

To prove atomicity we order the operations with respect to the timestamps associated with the written values. For each execution of the algorithm there must exist a partial order \prec on the operations that satisfy conditions A1, A2, and A3 given in Section 2. Let ts_π be the the timestamp at the completion of π when π is a write, and the timestamp associated with the returned value when π is a read. We now define the partial order as follows. For two operations π_1 and π_2 , when π_1 is any operation and π_2 is a write, we let $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ if $ts_{\pi_1} < ts_{\pi_2}$. For two operations π_1 and π_2 , when π_1 is a write and π_2 is a read we let $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ if $ts_{\pi_1} \leq ts_{\pi_2}$. The rest of the order is established by transitivity, without ordering the reads with the same timestamps. We now state the following lemmas (detailed proofs are given in the the full paper [7]).

Lemma 1. *In any execution ξ of ERATO, if a read ρ succeeds a write operation ω that writes timestamp ts , i.e. $\omega \rightarrow \rho$, and returns a timestamp ts' , then $ts' \geq ts$.*

Lemma 2. *In any execution ξ of ERATO, if ρ_1 and ρ_2 are two read operations such that ρ_1 precedes ρ_2 , i.e., $\rho_1 \rightarrow \rho_2$, and ρ_1 returns timestamp ts_1 , then ρ_2 returns a timestamp ts_2 , s.t. $ts_2 \geq ts_1$.*

Theorem 1. *Algorithm ERATO implements an atomic SWMR object.*

Proof. We now use the lemmas above and the partial order definition to reason about each of the three conditions A1, A2 and A3.

A1 For any $\pi_1, \pi_2 \in \Pi$ such that $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$, it cannot be that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$. When the two operations π_1 and π_2 are reads and $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 2 it follows that the timestamp of π_2 is no less than the one of π_1 , $ts_{\pi_2} \geq ts_{\pi_1}$. If $ts_{\pi_2} > ts_{\pi_1}$ then by the ordering definition $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ is satisfied. When $ts_{\pi_2} = ts_{\pi_1}$ then the ordering is not defined, thus it cannot be the case that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$. If π_2 is a write, the sole writer generates a new timestamp by incrementing the largest timestamp in the system. By well-formedness (see Section 2), any timestamp generated in any write operation that precedes π_2 must be smaller than ts_{π_2} . Since $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$, then it holds that $ts_{\pi_1} < ts_{\pi_2}$. Hence, by the ordering definition it cannot be the case that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$. Lastly, when π_2 is a read and π_1 a write and $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 1 it follows that $ts_{\pi_2} \geq ts_{\pi_1}$. By the ordering definition, it cannot hold that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$ in this case either.

A2 For any write $\omega \in \Pi$ and any operation $\pi \in \Pi$, then either $\omega \prec \pi$ or $\pi \prec \omega$. If the timestamp returned from ω is greater than the one returned from π , i.e. $ts_\omega > ts_\pi$, then $\pi \prec \omega$ follows directly. Similarly, if $ts_\omega < ts_\pi$ holds, then $\omega \prec \pi$ follows. If $ts_\omega = ts_\pi$, then it must be that π is a read and π discovered ts_ω in a quorum view QV(1) or QV(3). Thus, $\omega \prec \pi$ follows.

A3 Every read operation returns the value of the last write preceding it according to \prec (or the initial value if there is no such write).

Let ω be the last write preceding read ρ . From our definition it follows that $ts_\rho \geq ts_\omega$. If $ts_\rho = ts_\omega$, then ρ returns the value conveyed by ω to some servers in a quorum Q , satisfying either QV(1) or QV(3). If $ts_\rho > ts_\omega$, then ρ obtains a larger timestamp, but such a timestamp can only be created by a write that succeeds ω , thus ω does not precede the read and this cannot be the case. Lastly, if $ts_\rho = 0$, no preceding writes exist, and ρ returns the initial value. \square

Communication and Message Complexity. By inspection of the code, write operations take 2 exchanges and read operations take either 2 or 3 exchanges. The message complexity of write operations is $2|\mathcal{S}|$ and of read operations is $|\mathcal{S}|^2 + 2|\mathcal{S}|$, as follows from the structure of the algorithm.

4 Algorithm ERATO-MW

We now aim for a MWMR algorithm that involves *two* or *three* communications exchanges per read operation and *four* exchanges per write operation. The read protocol of algorithm ERATO relies on the fact of the sole writer in the system: based on the distribution of the timestamp in a quorum Q , if the reader knows that the write operation is not complete, then any previous write is complete (by well-formedness). In the MWMR setting this does not hold due to the possibility of concurrent writes. Consequently, algorithm ERATO-MW, in order to allow operations to terminate in either *two* or *three* communication exchanges, adapts the read protocol from algorithm OHMAM in combination with the iterative technique using quorum views of CWFR. The latter approach not only predicts the completion status of a write operation, but also detects the last potentially complete write operation. The code is given in in Algorithm 2.

4.1 Detailed Algorithm Description

To impose an ordering on the values written by the writers we associate each value with a tag tg defined as the pair (ts, id) , where ts is a timestamp and id the identifier of a writer. Tags are ordered lexicographically (cf. [13]).

Reader Protocol. Readers use state variables similarly to algorithm ERATO. Reader r broadcasts a `readRequest` message to all servers, then awaits either (a) `readRelay` messages from some quorum, or (b) `readAck` messages from some quorum (L10-14). The key departure here is in how the reader handles case (a) when QV(2) is detected, which indicates that the write associated with the *maximum* tag is not complete. Here the reader considers past history and discovers the tag associated with the last complete write. This is accomplished in an iterative manner, by removing the servers that respond with the maximum tag in the

Algorithm 2 Reader, Writer and Server Protocols for MWMR algorithm ERATO-MW

```

1: At each reader  $r$ 
2: Variables:
3:  $v \in V$ ;  $read\_op \in \mathbb{N}$ ;  $minTAG, maxTAG \in T$ 
4:  $RR, RA, maxACK \subseteq S \times M$  init  $\emptyset$ 
5:  $RRsrv, RAsrv, maxTGsrv \subseteq S$  init  $\emptyset$ 
6: Initialization:
7:  $minTAG \leftarrow \langle 0, 0 \rangle$ ,  $maxTAG \leftarrow \langle 0, 0 \rangle$ 
8:  $v \leftarrow \perp$ ,  $read\_op \leftarrow 0$ 
9: function READ
10:    $read\_op \leftarrow read\_op + 1$ 
11:    $(RR, RA, maxACK) \leftarrow (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$ 
12:    $(RRsrv, RAsrv, maxTGsrv) \leftarrow (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)$ 
13:   bcast ( $\langle readRequest, r, read\_op \rangle$ ) to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
14:   wait until  $\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RRsrv \vee Q \subseteq RAsrv$ 
15:   if  $(\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RAsrv)$  then
16:      $minTAG \leftarrow \min\{(m.ts, m.id) :$ 
17:        $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q\}$ 
18:     return  $(m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q$ 
19:        $\wedge (m.ts, m.id) = minTAG)$ 
20:   else if  $(\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq RRsrv)$  then
21:     while  $(Q \neq \emptyset)$  do
22:        $maxTAG \leftarrow \max\{(m.ts, m.id) :$ 
23:          $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q\}$ 
24:        $maxACK \leftarrow \{(s, m) \in RR : s \in Q \wedge$ 
25:          $(m.ts, m.id) = maxTAG\}$ 
26:        $maxTGsrv \leftarrow \{s \in Q :$ 
27:          $(s, m) \in maxACK\}$ 
28:       if  $Q \subseteq maxTGsrv$  then
29:         /** Qview1**//
30:         return  $(m.v$  s.t.  $(s, m) \in maxACK)$ 
31:       if  $\exists Q' \in \mathbb{Q}, Q' \neq Q : Q' \cap Q$ 
32:          $\subseteq maxTGsrv$  then /**Qview3**//
33:         wait until
34:            $\exists Q'' \in \mathbb{Q} : Q'' \subseteq RAsrv$ 
35:            $minTAG \leftarrow \min\{(m.ts, m.id) :$ 
36:              $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q''\}$ 
37:           return  $(m.v$  s.t.,  $(s, m) \in RA \wedge s \in Q''$ 
38:              $\wedge (m.ts, m.id) = minTAG)$ 
39:         else /** Qview2**//
40:            $Q \leftarrow Q - maxTGsrv$ 
41:   Upon receive  $m$  from  $s$ 
42:   if  $m.read\_op = read\_op$  then
43:     if  $m.type = readRelay$  then
44:        $RR \leftarrow RR \cup \{(s, m)\}$ 
45:        $RRsrv \leftarrow RRsrv \cup \{s\}$ 
46:     else // readAck //
47:        $RA \leftarrow RA \cup \{(s, m)\}$ 
48:        $RAsrv \leftarrow RAsrv \cup \{s\}$ 
49: At each writer  $w$ 
50: Variables:
51:  $ts \in \mathbb{N}, v \in V, write\_op \in \mathbb{N}, maxTS \in \mathbb{N}$ 
52:  $Acks \subseteq S \times M$  init  $\emptyset$ ;  $AcksSrv \subseteq S$  init  $\emptyset$ 
53: Initialization:
54:  $ts \leftarrow 0$ ,  $v \leftarrow \perp$ ,  $write\_op \leftarrow 0$ ,  $maxTS \leftarrow 0$ 
55: function WRITE( $val : input$ )
56:    $write\_op \leftarrow write\_op + 1$ 
57:    $(Acks, AcksSrv) \leftarrow (\emptyset, \emptyset)$ 
58:   bcast ( $\langle writeDiscover, write\_op, w \rangle$ ) to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
59:   wait until  $(\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq AcksSrv)$ 
60:    $maxTS \leftarrow \max\{(m.ts) :$ 
61:      $(s, m) \in Acks \wedge s \in Q\}$ 
62:    $(ts, id, v) \leftarrow (maxTS + 1, i, val)$ 
63:    $write\_op \leftarrow write\_op + 1$ 
64:    $(Acks, AcksSrv) \leftarrow (\emptyset, \emptyset)$ 
65:   bcast ( $\langle writeRequest, ts, v, w, write\_op \rangle$ ) to  $\mathcal{S}$ 
66:   wait until  $(\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq AcksSrv)$ 
67:   return()
68: Upon receive  $m$  from  $s$ 
69: if  $m.write\_op = write\_op$  then
70:    $Acks \leftarrow Acks \cup \{(s, m)\}$ 
71:    $AcksSrv \leftarrow AcksSrv \cup \{s\}$ 
72: At server  $s$ 
73: Variables and Initialization:
74:  $ts \in \mathbb{N}$  init 0;  $id \in \mathcal{W}$  init  $\perp$ ;  $v \in V$  init  $\perp$ 
75:  $operations : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$  init  $0^{|\mathcal{R}|}$ 
76:  $write\_ops : \mathcal{W} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$  init  $0^{|\mathcal{W}|}$ 
77:  $relays : \mathcal{R} \rightarrow 2^S$  init  $\emptyset^{|\mathcal{R}|}$ 
78:  $D \subseteq S$  init  $\{s : (\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q}), (s, s_i \in Q)\}$ 
79: Upon receive ( $\langle writeDiscover, write\_op, w \rangle$ )
80: send ( $\langle discoverAck, ts, id, s_i \rangle$ ) to  $w$ 
81: Upon receive
82: ( $\langle writeRequest, ts', v', id', write\_op, w \rangle$ )
83: if  $write\_ops[w] < write\_op$  then
84:    $write\_ops[w] \leftarrow write\_op$ 
85:   if  $(ts < ts') \vee (ts = ts' \wedge id < id')$  then
86:      $(ts, id, v) \leftarrow (ts', id', v')$ 
87:   send ( $\langle writeAck, write\_op, s \rangle$ ) to  $w$ 
88: Upon receive ( $\langle readRequest, r, read\_op \rangle$ )
89: bcast ( $\langle readRelay, ts, id, v, r, read\_op, s \rangle$ ) to  $D \cup r$ 
90: Upon receive ( $\langle readRelay, ts', id', v', r, read\_op, s \rangle$ )
91: if  $(ts < ts') \vee (ts = ts' \wedge id < id')$  then
92:    $(ts, id, v) \leftarrow (ts', id', v')$ 
93: if  $(operations[r] < read\_op)$  then
94:    $operations[r_i] \leftarrow read\_op$ ;  $relays[r] \leftarrow \emptyset$ .
95: if  $(operations[r] = read\_op)$  then
96:    $relays[r] \leftarrow relays[r] \cup \{s\}$ 
97: if  $(\exists Q \in \mathbb{Q} : Q \subseteq relays[r])$  then
98:   send ( $\langle readAck, ts, id, v, read\_op, s \rangle$ ) to  $r$ 

```

responding quorum Q and repeating the analysis (L21-40). During the iterative process, if r detects QV(1) it returns the value associated with the *maximum* tag discovered during the current iteration. If no iteration yields QV(1), then eventually r observes QV(3). In the last case, QV(3) is detected when a single server

remains in some intersection of Q . If so, the reader waits `readAck` messages to arrive from some quorum, and returns the value associated with the *minimum* tag. If case (b) happens before case (a), then r proceeds identically as in the case where $QV(3)$ is detected (L15-19).

Writer Protocol. Similarly to the four-exchange implementation [13], a writer broadcasts a `writeDiscover` message to all servers, and awaits “fresh” `discoverAck` messages from some quorum Q (L56-59). Among these responses the writer finds the *maximum* timestamp, $maxTS$, increments it, and associates it and its own id with the new value by broadcasting the new timestamp, its id, and the new value in a `writeRequest` message to all servers. The write completes when `writeAck` messages are received from some quorum Q (L61-66).

Server Protocol. Servers react to messages from readers exactly as in Algorithm 1. We now describe how the messages from writers are handled.

(1) Upon receiving message $\langle \text{writeDiscover}, write_op, w \rangle$, server s replies with a `discoverAck` message containing its local tag and value. (L79-80).

(2) Upon receiving message $\langle \text{writeRequest}, ts', id', v', write_op, w \rangle$, server s compares lexicographically its local tag with the received one. If $(ts, id) < (ts', id')$, then s updates its local information and replies using `writeAck` message (L82-87).

4.2 Correctness and Complexity

Termination of algorithm ERATO-MW is satisfied with respect to our failure model. Atomicity (safety) is reasoned about as in Section 3.2, except using *tags* instead of timestamps. (Complete proofs are given in the the full paper [7]).

Lemma 3. *In any execution ξ of ERATO-MW, if a write ω writes tag tg' and succeeds a read operation ρ that returns a tag tg , i.e., $\rho \rightarrow \omega$, then $tg' > tg$.*

Lemma 4. *In any execution ξ of ERATO-MW, if a write ω_1 writes tag tg_1 and precedes a write ω_2 that writes tag tg_2 , i.e., $\omega_1 \rightarrow \omega_2$, then $tg_2 > tg_1$.*

Lemma 5. *In any execution ξ of ERATO-MW, if a read ρ succeeds a write operation ω that writes tag tg , i.e. $\omega \rightarrow \rho$, and returns a tag tg' , then $tg' \geq tg$.*

Lemma 6. *In any execution ξ of ERATO-MW, if ρ_1 and ρ_2 are two read operations s.t. ρ_1 precedes ρ_2 , i.e., $\rho_1 \rightarrow \rho_2$, and ρ_1 returns tag tg_1 , then ρ_2 returns a tag tg_2 , s.t. $tg_2 \geq tg_1$.*

Theorem 2. *Algorithm ERATO-MW implements an atomic MWMMR object.*

Proof. We use the above lemmas and the operations order definition to reason about each of the three atomicity conditions A1, A2 and A3.

A1 For any $\pi_1, \pi_2 \in \Pi$ such that $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$, it cannot be that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$. If both π_1 and π_2 are writes and $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 4 it follows that $tg_{\pi_2} > tg_{\pi_1}$. From the definition of order \prec we have $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$. When π_1 is a write, π_2 a read and $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 5 it follows that $tg_{\pi_2} \geq tg_{\pi_1}$. By definition $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ holds. If π_1 is a read, π_2 is a write and

$\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 3 it follows that π_2 returns a tag tg_{π_2} s.t. $tg_{\pi_2} > tg_{\pi_1}$. By the order definition $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ is satisfied. If both π_1 and π_2 are reads and $\pi_1 \rightarrow \pi_2$ holds, then from Lemma 6 it follows that $tg_{\pi_2} \geq tg_{\pi_1}$. If $tg_{\pi_2} > tg_{\pi_1}$, then by the ordering definition $\pi_1 \prec \pi_2$ holds. When $tg_{\pi_2} = tg_{\pi_1}$, then the ordering is not defined, thus it cannot be that $\pi_2 \prec \pi_1$.

A2 For any write $\omega \in \Pi$ and any operation $\pi \in \Pi$, then either $\omega \prec \pi$ or $\pi \prec \omega$. If $tg_\omega > tg_\pi$, then $\pi \prec \omega$ follows directly. If $tg_\omega < tg_\pi$ holds, then it follows that $\omega \prec \pi$. When $ts_\omega = ts_\pi$ holds, then because all writer tags are unique (each server increments timestamps monotonically, and the server ids disambiguate among servers) π can only be a read. Since π is a read and the distribution of the tag written by ω satisfies either QV(1) or QV(3), it follows that $\omega \prec \pi$.

A3 Every read operation returns the value of the last write preceding it according to \prec (or the initial value if there is no such write).

Let ω be the last write preceding read ρ . From our definition it follows that $tg_\rho \geq tg_\omega$. If $tg_\rho = tg_\omega$, then ρ returned a value written by ω in some servers in a quorum Q . Read ρ either was *fast* and during the iterative analysis it noticed a distribution of the tags in Q that satisfied QV(1) or ρ was *slow* and waited for readAck messages from a full quorum Q . In the latter, the intersection properties of quorums ensure that ω was the last complete write. If $tg_\rho > tg_\omega$ holds, it must be the case that there is a write ω' that wrote tg_ρ and by definition it must hold that $\omega \prec \omega' \prec \rho$. Thus, ω is not the preceding write and this cannot be the case. Lastly, if $tg_\rho = 0$, no preceding writes exist, and ρ returns the initial value. \square

Communication and Message Complexity. Writes take 4 exchanges and reads either 2 or 3 exchanges. Message complexity of writes is $4|\mathcal{S}|$ and of reads $|\mathcal{S}|^2 + 2|\mathcal{S}|$. This follows from the structure of the algorithm.

5 Empirical Evaluations

We now compare the algorithms using the NS3 discrete event simulator [1]. The following SWMR algorithms ERATO, ABD [2], OHSAM [9], and SLIQ [6], and the corresponding MWMR algorithms: ERATO-MW, ABD-MW [13], OHMAM [9], and CwFR [5] were simulated. For comparison, we implemented benchmark LB that mimics the minimum message requirements: LB does two exchanges for reads and writes, and neither performs any computation nor ensures consistency.

We developed two topologies that use the same array of routers, but differ in the deployment of server and client nodes. Clients are connected to routers over 5Mbps links with 4ms delay and the routers over 10Mbps links with 6ms delay. In *Series* topology, Fig.2(a), a server is connected to each router over 10Mbps bandwidth with 2ms delay, modeling a network where servers are separated and appear to be in different networks. In *Star* topology, Fig.2(b), servers are connected to a single router over 50Mbps links with 2ms delay, modeling a network where servers are in close proximity and well-connected, e.g., a datacenter. Clients are located uniformly with respect to the routers.

Performance. We assess algorithms in terms of *operation latency* that depends on communication delays and local computation time. For operation latency we

combine two clocks: the simulation clock to measure communication delays, and a real time clock for computation delays. The sum of the two yields latency.

Experimentation Setup. To subject the system to high communication traffic, no failures are assumed (ironically, crashes reduce network traffic). Communication is via point-to-point bidirectional links implemented with a DropTail queue.

Scenarios. The scenarios are designed to test (i) the scalability of the algorithms as the number of readers, writers, and servers increases; (ii) the contention effect on efficiency, and (iii) the effects of chosen topologies on the efficiency. For scalability we test with the number of readers $|\mathcal{R}|$ from the set $\{10, 20, 40, 80\}$ and the number of servers $|\mathcal{S}|$ from the set $\{9, 16, 25, 36\}$. Algorithms are evaluated with matrix quorums (unions of rows and columns). For the MWMR setting we range the number of writers $|\mathcal{W}|$ over the set $\{10, 20, 40\}$. We issue reads (and writes) every $rInt$ (and $wInt$ respectively) from the set of $\{2, 4\}$ seconds. To test contention we define two invocation schemes: *fixed* and *stochastic*. In the *fixed* scheme all operations are scheduled periodically at a constant interval. In the *stochastic* scheme reads are scheduled randomly from the intervals $[1 \dots rInt]$ and write operations from the intervals $[1 \dots wInt]$.

Results. We note that generally the new algorithms outperform the competition. A closer examination yields the following observations.

Scalability: Increased number of readers and servers increases latency in both settings. Observe Fig. 5(a),(b) for SWMR and Fig. 5(e),(f) for MWMR algorithms. Not surprisingly, latency is better for smaller numbers of readers, writers, and servers. However, the relative performance of the algorithms remains the same.

Contention: The efficiency of the algorithms is examined under different concurrency schemes. We notice that in the *stochastic* scheme reads complete faster than in the *fixed* scheme – Fig. 5(b) and 5(c) for the SWMR and Fig. 5(f) and 5(g) for the MWMR setting. This outcome is expected as the *fixed* scheme causes congestion. For the *stochastic* scheme the invocation time intervals are distributed uniformly (randomness prevents the operations from being invoked simultaneously), and this reduces congestion in the network and improves latency.

Fig. 2. Simulated topologies.

Fig. 3. Simulation results for SWMR (a-d) and MWMR (e-g). Horizontal axis is the number of readers. Vertical axis is latency.

Topology: Topology substantially impacts performance and the behavior of the algorithms. This can be seen in Figures 5(b) and 5(d) for the SWMR setting, and Figures 5(f) and 5(h) for the MWMR setting. The results show clearly that the proposed algorithms outperform the competition in the *Star* topology, where servers are well-connected using high bandwidth links.

6 Conclusions

We focused on the problem of emulating atomic read/write shared objects in the asynchronous, crash-prone, message-passing settings with the goal of synthesizing algorithms where read operations can *always* terminate in *less* than two communication round-trips. We presented such algorithms for the SWMR and MWMR models. We rigorously reasoned about the correctness of our algorithms. The algorithms impose no constraints on the number of readers, and no constraints on the number of writers (in the MWMR model). The algorithms are shown to be optimal in terms of *communication exchanges* with unconstrained participation. The empirical study demonstrates the practicality of the new algorithms, and identifies settings in which their performance is clearly superior.

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